

Analysing the Studies Conducted in the Field of Creative Writing within the Scope of Classroom Education between 2010-2024

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Article Info

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the studies conducted in the field of creative writing in Turkey between 2010 and 2024. Keywords such as "creative writing", "creativity" and "classroom education" were used in the concept search to identify studies in this field, and 46 studies were found. The research data was collected between 10 October 2024 and 20 November 2024 via the Google Scholar, Dergipark and Higher Education Council (YÖK) National Thesis Centre websites. The research is qualitative, and the data was collected using the document analysis technique. The data was collected using the "Article-Thesis Review Form". Of the 46 studies comprising the data set, 24 were articles and 22 were theses. Looking at the distribution of studies by year, it was found that the highest number of articles were published in 2018 and 2022, while the highest number of theses were completed in 2019. Considering the objectives of the dataset, the aim was to examine the effect of creative drama on writing and creative writing development. In these studies, primary school pupils were mostly selected as the sample, and qualitative research methods were used. It is hoped that this study will prove useful in guiding future research and applications by revealing current trends in the field of creative writing.

Keywords: Creative Writing, Classroom Education, Content Analysis.

Öz

Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye'de 2010-2024 yılları arasında yaratıcı yazma alanında yapılan çalışmalarını incelemektir. Bu alandaki çalışmalarını belirlemek için kavram taramasında 'yaratıcı yazma', 'yaratıcılık' ve 'sınıf içi eğitim' gibi anahtar kelimeler kullanılmış ve 46 çalışmaya ulaşılmıştır. Araştırmanın verileri 10.10.2024 ile 20.11.2024 tarihleri arasında Google Akademik, Dergipark ve Yüksek Öğretim Kurumu (YÖK) Ulusal Tez Merkezi web sitesi üzerinden toplanmıştır. Araştırma nitel bir araştırmadır ve veriler doküman analizi tekniği ile toplanmıştır. Veriler 'Makale-Tez İnceleme Formu' aracılığıyla toplanmıştır. Veri setini oluşturan 46 çalışmanın 24'ünün makale, 22'sinin ise tez olduğu görülmüştür. Çalışmaların yıllara göre dağılımına bakıldığında makale türünde en çok çalışmanın 2018 ve 2022 yıllarında, tez türünde ise 2019 yılında yapıldığı tespit edilmiştir. Veri setinin amaçları göz önüne alındığında yaratıcı dramının yazma ve yaratıcı yazma gelişimine etkisinin incelenmesi hedeflenmiştir. Bu çalışmalarda örneklem olarak çoğunlukla ilkökul öğrencileri belirlenmiş ve nitel araştırma yöntemleri kullanılmıştır. Bu çalışmanın, yaratıcı yazma alanındaki mevcut eğilimleri ortaya koyarak gelecekte yapılacak araştırmalara ve uygulamalara yön verme konusunda faydalı olması düşünülmektedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Yaratıcı Yazma, Sınıf Eğitimi, İçerik Analizi.

1.Introduction

Although there is no precise definition of the concept of creativity in the literature, in the dictionary of the Turkish Language Association, the word "creativity" is defined as "the act of creating something new that has not been seen until then by making use of intelligence, thought and imagination; the act of causing or causing something to happen" (Türk Dil Kurumu (TDK), 1999, p.2395-2396); creativity is defined as "the ability to design, find and realise something new and original, which is accepted to exist in everyone" (TDK, 1999, p.2386). According to this definition, individuals with developed creativity skills are expected to create original content based on their own imagination.

Writing skill is defined in the Turkish Dictionary (2023) as "writing work, tahrir". When the related literature is reviewed, it is to produce symbols to express our thoughts about writing skill (Akyol, 2011). The main purpose of teaching writing is to enable students to express what they want to express, their thoughts and feelings with symbols. Gaining and displaying writing skills is the most difficult language skill to be applied by students (Duran, 2010.) Writing is the product of thought. Before writing, planning, organising and memorising are required. For this reason, it is known to be more difficult than the other three basic skills. Writing consists of 5 stages. These are; pre-writing preparation, drafting, revising and editing, redaction (correction according to grammar rules) and publishing stages (Akyol & Yıldız, 2018). The writing process is also handled in different categories. According to Güneş (2007), it is stated as pre-writing, writing moment and post-writing stages. While the pre-writing stage allows the individual to make mental preparation, the post-writing stage is a stage that allows the individual to perform procedures for the evaluation of the text. It is expected that the individual who successfully completes these stages will not have problems in the writing process.

Creative writing is the act of expressing the same ideas in writing in a unique way that has not been put forward before. Creative writing is the work of putting forward the writer's thoughts, feelings, experiences and any thought product that the writer wants to convey in a unique way. Creative writing is a two-dimensional personal skill formed by the combination of creative thinking and writing. (Taşkesen & Uzuner Yurt, 2018.) Creative writing is also an activity that develops the individual's original thinking and imagination.

When the researches in the literature are examined, it is seen that different practices are carried out to improve writing skills. Around these studies (Gökçe, 2020; Kasap, 2019; Korkmaz, 2015; Maden & Durukan, 2010; Temizkan, 2011; Tonyalı, 2010), the contributions of creative writing practices to writing skills were determined.

When the researches conducted in recent years are examined, it is seen that the number of studies on creative writing in our country has increased. The articles and thesis studies produced reveal the developments in the literature. This study was conducted to determine the research trends of the articles and thesis studies produced from the researches on creative writing conducted in the field of classroom education in our country in the last 14 years. In this study (Tanju Aslışen & Hakkoymaz, 2020), the distribution of articles and theses on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010 and 2024 were examined in terms of their aims, study groups, research methods, research designs and data collection tools. The most important aims of this study are to determine the status of the researches conducted in this field for academicians, classroom teachers and parents who want to conduct studies on creative writing and to guide new researches.

2. Method

2.1. Design

In this study, which was conducted to determine the trends of the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education in Turkey between 2010 and 2024, the data were collected through document analysis, one of the qualitative research methods. Document analysis is the analysis of written sources containing information about the phenomenon under investigation (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2018). When using the document review method, it consists of certain stages such as coding, thematising, categorising and interpreting the findings (Creswell, 2013).

2.2. Data Set of the Research

In the Google Scholar, Dergipark and Yüksek Öğretim Kurumu (YÖK) Ulusal Tez Merkezi databases were searched to determine the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education. While selecting the data set of the research, it was determined as a criterion that the theses and articles should include the subject of creative writing, should only be within the scope of classroom education subject area, should be registered in Dergipark and Yüksek Öğretim Kurumu (YÖK) Ulusal Tez Merkezi and should have access permission. In this context, a total of 46 studies, 24 articles and 22 thesis, which meet the specified criteria, constitute the data set of the study.

2.3. Data Collection

In the first stage of document analysis, the studies included in the data set were accessed from the Ulusal Tez Merkezi and Dergipark databases. Keywords such as "creative writing", "creativity" and "classroom education" were used during the concept search and 46 studies were reached. The data of the study were collected between 10.10.2024 and 20.11.2024 via Dergipark and YÖK Ulusal Tez Merkezi website. The studies conducted until the end of October 2024 were included in the scope of this study, and the studies in the data set obtained for the purpose of the study were grouped in terms of their aims, study groups, methods, designs and data collection tools.

2.4. Analysing the Data

In the analysis and interpretation of the data obtained in this research, "content analysis", one of the data analysis methods in qualitative research, was used. Content analysis method was used to analyse and interpret the data of the research. In this method, it is aimed to reach concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016, p.242).

As the first step of the study, the studies in the data set obtained for the purpose of the study were coded in terms of their types. In the tabulation of the data, each study was coded according to its type (e.g. M1: Article numbered 1; T1: Thesis numbered 1, etc.).

Reliability in content analysis is achieved through coding based on categories. It is important to determine the categories clearly (Gökçe, 2006, p.83). Article Review Form was developed by the researchers in order to code the articles included in the study. The data analysed by content analysis were grouped according to themes and frequencies (f) and percentages (%) were given. In this form, information about the author, names of the studies, authors, aims, study groups, methods, designs and data collection tools were included. Microsoft Excel was used for coding in the process of analysing the studies.

3. Findings

In this part of the study, the findings of the data set obtained in order to determine the trends of the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education in Turkey between 2010 and 2024 are presented. It is presented by considering the distribution of the studies according to years, aims, study groups, research methods, research designs and data collection tools.

Table 1 shows the distribution of the data set obtained according to years and types.

Table 1.

Distribution of the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education according to years

TYPE	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Total
Article	0	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	4	1	1	2	4	1	2	24
																Total
																46

When Table 1 is analysed, it is seen that 24 of the studies constituting the data set of the research are articles and 22 of them are theses. In the light of this information, it was seen that the article type was more common among the studies conducted in Turkey in the last 14 years. Looking at the distribution of studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education according to years, it was determined that the most studies were conducted in 2018 (n = 4) and 2022 (n = 4) in article type and 2019 (n = 6) in thesis type.

The distribution of 46 studies on creative writing conducted in the field of classroom education in Turkey between 2010 and 2024 according to their aims is shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Distribution of the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education according to their aims

Objectives	Studies	Frequency	%
The effect of creative drama on the development of writing and creative writing	M4, M13, M14, M17, T2, T3, T6, T12, T13,	9	% 19,57
To examine the effect of creative reading and creative writing activities on creative writing skills of primary school students	M15, M19, M22, T10, T19, T22	6	% 13,04
To analyse the creative thinking and creative writing skills of classroom teachers and to evaluate their opinions and thoughts	M7, M8, M9, M10, M23	5	% 10,87
The effect of digital stories on creative writing skills	T4, T7, T14, T20,	4	% 8,70
The effect of reflective thinking on creative writing	M2, M11, T9	3	% 6,52
The effect of process-based writing models on creative writing skills	M5, T11	2	% 4,35
Attitudes towards writing in creative writing activities	M21, M24	2	% 4,35

Analysing articles on primary school students' writing skills according to thematic content analysis method, one of the types of content analysis	T1,T17	2	%4,35
Examining students' social perceptions and stereotypes through creative writing	M16	1	%2,17
To determine the effect of using a Turkish dictionary and creating a word book on creative writing	M18	1	%2,17
To examine the creative writing tendencies, writing concerns and attitudes of gifted students	M20	1	%2,17
The effect of using artificial intelligence on creative writing	M12	1	%2,17
The effect of activity-based poems on creative writing skills	T5	1	%2,17
The effect of teaching the value of responsibility with activities created with creative writing techniques on students' level of responsibility	T8	1	%2,17
Investigating the effect of pen pal method on primary school 4th grade students' writing anxiety and creative writing skills	T15,	1	%2,17
To reveal the effects of musical writing activities on writing anxiety, writing attitude and creative writing skills of primary school fourth grade students	T16	1	%2,17
To develop students' creative thinking skills in this area by applying linguistic creative writing activities	T18	1	%2,17
To determine the effect of blog writing activities on the writing skills and writing attitudes of primary school 4th grade students	T21	1	%2,17
The effect of creative writing on children's language development	M1	1	%2,17

The effect between writing dispositions and writing achievements	M3	1	%2,17
Pre-service teacher views on written expression	M6	1	%2,17
Total		46	%100

When Table 2 is analysed, it is seen that studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education in 2010-2024 were conducted for different purposes. Accordingly, it was determined that the studies conducted for "the effect of creative drama on the development of writing and creative writing" had the highest frequency with 19,57%. However, it is seen that 13,04% of the studies were carried out with the aim of "examining the effect of creative reading and creative writing studies on the creative writing skills of primary school students". On the other hand, "Examining students' social perceptions and stereotypes through creative writing", "Determining the effect of using a Turkish dictionary and creating a word book on creative writing", "Examining the creative writing tendencies, writing concerns and attitudes of gifted students", "The effect of using artificial intelligence on creative writing", "The effect of activity-based poems on creative writing skills", "The effect of teaching responsibility value with activities created with creative writing techniques on students' responsibility level", "The effect of pen pal method on primary school 4th grade students' writing concerns and the effect of pen pal method on primary school 4th grade students' writing concerns and creative writing skills". grade students' writing anxiety and creative writing skills", "To reveal the effects of musical writing activities on writing anxiety, writing attitude and creative writing skills of primary school fourth grade students", "The development of students' creative thinking skills in this field by applying linguistic creative writing activities", "The effect of blogging activities on primary school 4th grade students' writing skills and writing skills", "The effect of blogging activities on primary school 4th grade students' writing skills and writing attitude". grade students' writing skills and writing attitudes", "The effect of creative writing on children's language development", "The effect between writing tendencies and writing achievements" and "Pre-service teacher views on written expression" were found to have the lowest frequency with 2,17%.

The distribution of the studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education conducted between 2010 and 2024 according to the study groups is given in Table 3.

Table 3.

Distribution of the study groups included in the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education

TYPE	Student	Teacher Candidate	Teacher	Literature Review	Total
Article	16	1	5	2	24
Thesis	21	0	1	0	22

When Table 3 is analysed, it is seen that studies were conducted with four groups: students, pre-service teachers, teachers and literature review. In the studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education in our country, it was determined that the most studied sample group was primary school students in article (n=16) and thesis (n=21) types. The least studied sample group was found to be pre-service teachers (n=1) in the article type and teachers (n=1) in the thesis type. In the thesis research type, it was determined that between the years 2010-2024, pre-service teachers and literature review were never used as a sample.

The methods of the studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010-2024 were analysed in three groups and presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Distribution of research methods used in studies on creative writing in classroom education

TYPE	Qualitative	Quantitative	Mixed
Article	9	8	7
Thesis	12	6	4

When Table 4 was analysed, it was seen that 21 of 46 studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010 and 2024 were conducted with qualitative, 14 with quantitative and 11 with mixed methods. It was seen that more qualitative (n=12) studies were conducted in thesis research type than articles, while quantitative (n=8) and mixed (n=7) studies were conducted in article type at most.

Table 5 shows the distribution of the studies conducted in the field of creative writing within the scope of classroom education according to research designs.

Table 5.*Distribution of studies on creative writing in classroom education according to research designs*

Research Designs	Studies	Frequency	%
Quasi-Experimental	M2, M4, M11, M14, M17, T3, T4, T7, T8, T9, T10, T14, T17, T20, T21	15	% 26,32
Experimental	M5, M7, M13, M15, M18, M20, T1, T2, T11, T13, T15, T16, T22	13	% 22,80
Document Analysis	M1, M6, M16, M19, T2, T12, T18	7	% 12,28
Semi-structured Interview	M6, M12, T5, T10, T12, T13, T19	7	% 12,28
Case Study	M10, M22, M23, T19, T20	5	% 8,77
Action Research	M9, T6	2	% 3,51
Parallel	M12, M19	2	% 3,51
Multiple Regression	M3	1	% 1,75
Embedded	M13	1	% 1,75
Phenomenology (Phenomonology)	M20	1	% 1,75
Thematic Content Analysis	M21	1	% 1,75
Descriptive Status	M8	1	% 1,75
Meta-Analysis	M24	1	% 1,75

*Since more than one design was used in some of the studies, the frequency value of each type in the table was formed according to the number of studies in which it was used. Therefore, the total number of studies analysed (n=46) and the sum of the frequencies given in the table are different from each other.

When Table 5 was examined, it was determined that the quasi-experimental design (f=15) was used the most among the research designs used in the analysed data set. It is seen that the quasi-experimental design is the design of 5 articles and 10 thesis research types. Then, it was determined that experimental (f=13) design was the design of 6 articles and 7 theses. On the other hand, it was determined that the least used designs were Multiple Regression, Embedded, Phenomenology, Thematic Content Analysis, Descriptive Case and Meta-analysis designs (f=1) in the least number of studies. All of the studies in which these designs were selected are article type studies.

The distribution of the studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education conducted between 2010 and 2024 according to data collection tools is given in Table 6.

Table 6.

Distribution of studies on creative writing in classroom education according to data collection tools

Data Collection Tools	Studies	Frequency	%
Scale	M3, M4, M5, M7, M11, M12, M13, M15, M17, M19, M20, T1, T7, T8, T10, T14, T15, T16, T17, T20, T22	21	% 32,81
Form	M9, M13, M14, M18, M21, M24, T3, T5, T6, T10, T11, T14, T15, T20	14	% 21,88
Interview	M6, M10, M22, M23, T2, T5, T6, T14, T18, T19	10	% 15,63
Rubrik	M2, T4, T5, T6, T7, T9, T13, T18,	8	% 12,50
Open-ended Question	M7, M8, M13, T15, T21	5	% 7,81
Document Review	M1, M6, M16, T10, T12	5	% 7,81
Survey	M7	1	%1,56

**Since more than one data collection tool was used in some of the studies, the frequency value of each type in the table was formed according to the number of studies in which it was used. Therefore, the total number of studies analysed (n=46) and the sum of the frequencies given in the table are different from each other.*

When Table 6 was analysed, it was seen that scale (f=21) was mostly used as data collection tool in the studies on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010-2024. When the types of studies using scales were analysed, it was found that 11 studies were in article type and 10 studies were in thesis type. Then, when the studies in which form (f=14) tool was used, it was seen that 6 studies were in article type and 8 studies were in thesis type. On the other hand, it was observed that the least data collection tool was questionnaire (f=1). It was determined that the research in which the questionnaire type was used was in the article type.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study was conducted to determine the research trends of the studies conducted in Turkey between 2010 and 2024 within the scope of classroom education on creative writing. In accordance with this purpose, a total of 46 studies were accessed from Google Scholar, Dergipark Yüksek Öğretim Kurumu (YÖK) Ulusal Tez Merkezi databases. It was seen that the article type of the studies reached was more than the thesis type. Looking at the distribution of these studies according to years, it was determined that no study was reached in 2010 and 2011 in the field of classroom education on creative writing in our country. It was determined that the years in which the studies were published the most were 2018, 2019 and 2022. This result is in parallel with the study of Karaoğlu and Çetinkaya (2022). Looking at the studies published on writing skills, it was concluded that the articles on the writing skills of primary school students between 2012-2020 were mostly published in 2018. The reason for this situation is thought to be that the concept of creative writing is more common in the literature. Since creative writing is considered as a skill that needs to be acquired by the little ones who are the adults of tomorrow, especially considering the 21st century skills, the concept of creative writing is also included in the field of classroom education.

In the majority of the studies examined, the aim was "Examining the effect of creative drama on the development of writing and creative writing" and this aim was followed by the aims of "Examining the effect of creative reading and creative writing activities on the creative writing skills of primary school students" and "Examining the creative thinking and creative writing skills of classroom teachers and evaluating their opinions and thoughts". However, the fact that there is only one article-type study aiming to examine the effect of artificial intelligence tools, which is today's technology, on creative writing can be considered as a negative situation in terms of the actuality of the subject of creative writing. Considering that creative writing is a situation that requires a process, it can be said that it is inevitable to measure or examine its effect within the framework of current issues in terms of being the subject of more long-term and up-to-date studies.

When the data group of the research was analysed in terms of sampling, it was determined that the study groups of the studies were mostly primary school students. Çoban (2022) states that the sample of the studies on creative writing is mostly primary and secondary school students. Considering that this study was conducted only in the field of classroom education, it can be said that it overlaps with Çoban's findings. Şentürk and Yazar (2021) analysed postgraduate studies on Turkish language teaching and stated that the most preferred sample was students and the least preferred sample was prospective teachers. The aforementioned finding was found to coincide with the findings of this study.

When the studies conducted in our country on creative writing in the field of classroom education were examined, it was seen that qualitative studies were used more numerically. In Karaoğlu and Çetinkaya's (2022) study examining the articles on the writing skills of primary school students, it was seen that quantitative researches were the most numerous. Karaoğlu and Çetinkaya stated that the reason for this is that the quantitative method is appropriate in determining the general status of students' writing skills. Since the subject of creative writing was handled in this study, it was concluded that more objective evaluation could be made with qualitative method. This study differs from the findings of Karaoğlu and Çetinkaya's study.

When the data set obtained in terms of research designs was analysed, it was found that the majority of the studies used quasi-experimental design, followed by experimental and document analysis methods. On the other hand, it was determined that the least used designs were Multiple Regression, Embedded, Phenomenology, Thematic Content Analysis, Descriptive Case and Meta-analysis designs. All of the studies in which these designs were selected are article type studies.

When the studies conducted in our country on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010 and 2024 were analysed in terms of data collection tools, it was found that the form and interview technique were used the most after the scale. On the other hand, questionnaire and document analysis techniques were used the least. Looking at the literature, Bolat and Tekin (2018) found that scale-type tools were more common as data collection tools in scale development studies in terms of the evaluation of writing teaching. The fact that Bağ and Çalık (2018) reached the most scale data collection tool in the data sets they obtained in their research on science teaching with 4th grade students is in parallel with the research findings.

As a result of the findings of this study, which examined the studies conducted in our country on creative writing in the field of classroom education between 2010-2024, it is thought that thesis studies should increase more. Since creative writing is an activity that can open students' horizons, it may be possible to provide more permanent learning about creative writing in the process.

4.1. Limitations and Future Directions

This study is limited to the articles and thesis studies on creative writing in the field of classroom teaching between 2010-2024. More detailed information can be accessed by increasing the scope of the study. It is important to conduct such studies at certain intervals in order to provide a perspective to researchers and stakeholders who will conduct research in this field.

5. Statement of Researchers

5.1. Researchers contribution rate statement:

Only one researcher was involved in the planning, execution and writing of this study.

5.2. Conflict statement

The researcher has no conflict of interest with other persons or organisations related to the research.

5.3. Support and thanks

No support was received from any institution, organisation or person in this research.

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